

Article

Edge Microservice Deployment and Management Using SDN-Enabled Whitebox Switches

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Abstract

This work advances a 6G-ready, micro-granular SDN fabric that unifies high-performance edge data planes with intent-driven, multi-domain orchestration and cloud offloading. First, edge and cell-site whiteboxes are upgraded with Smart Network Interface Cards and embedded AI accelerators, enabling line-rate processing of data flows and on-box learning/inference directly in the data plane. This pushes functions such as traffic classification, telemetry, and anomaly mitigation to the point of ingress, reducing latency and backhaul load. Second, an SDN controller, i.e., ETSI TeraFlowSDN, is extended to deliver multi-domain SDN orchestration with native lifecycle management (LCM) for whitebox Network Operating Systems—covering onboarding, configuration-drift control, rolling upgrades/rollbacks, and policy-guarded compliance—so operators can reliably manage heterogeneous edge fleets at scale. Third, the SDN controller incorporates a new NFV-O client that seamlessly offloads network services—such as ML pipelines or NOS components—to telco clouds via an NFV orchestrator (e.g., ETSI Open Source MANO), enabling elastic placement and scale-out across the edge–cloud continuum. Together, these contributions deliver an open, programmable platform that couples in-situ acceleration with closed-loop, intent-based orchestration and elastic cloud resources, targeting demonstrable gains in end-to-end latency, throughput, operational agility, and energy efficiency for emerging 6G services.

Keywords: 6G networks; software-defined networking; SmartNICs; whitebox switches; NFV orchestration

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1. Introduction

Emerging applications such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Virtual Reality, 6G networks, and Internet of Things (IoT) require a high volume of traffic, with an estimated 500 billion devices connected to the internet by 2030. This is 59 times greater than the expected world population. 6G is required to support 107 devices per square kilometer, ten times larger than the requirement of 5G [1]. Furthermore, 5G networks have shown significant improvements over existing systems, but this is not enough to fulfill the demands of future

emerging networks and automation systems. Although 5G introduced new frequency bands, advanced spectrum usage and management, and integration of licensed and unlicensed bands, the rapid convergence of data-centric and automated systems exceeds these capabilities. The evolution to 6G networks demands newly programmable and intelligent infrastructures to manage complex network domains from the access and edge networks to the transport and cloud [2].

To support 6G, networks require programmable data planes that allow dynamic reconfiguration. Previously, the data plane functionality was integrated into the device hardware and software, and limited to switches. This programmability provides an opportunity for a new range of applications within the data plane, such as advanced monitoring and telemetry, large-scale data processing, machine learning, or even fully functional key-value stores implemented inside network devices, with zero interference from the control plane. While data plane programmability was initially focused on switches only, nowadays several devices and functions allow low-level programmability, such as Smart Programmable Network Interface Cards (known as SmartNICs) at the network edge [3].

In recent years, Intel developed several Network Interface Cards (NICs) focusing on the enhancement of firewall and Quality of Service (QoS) capabilities, which were limited to data paths defined by traditional five-tuple filtering (Source IP, Destination IP, Source Port, Destination Port, and L4 Protocol) and VLAN classification. This restriction limits Deep Packet Inspection in virtualized 5G/6G environments, where the traffic is deeply encapsulated. To address these challenges, the networking industry is shifting from traditional NICs to SmartNICs. SmartNICs are based on Field-Programmable Gate Arrays and Data Processing Units (DPUs), offloading processing from the CPU, and enabling better programmability [4].

To support automation in 6G, it is critical to ensure that Network Operating Systems (NOSs) can efficiently and automatically manage the lifecycle of devices [5]. Having zero-touch provisioning systems (ZTP) implemented eases automation and configuration on network devices without the need for human intervention. This network automation service lessens the efforts on configuration adjustments and timely updates, improving the overall efficiency and reliability of network infrastructures [6].

Adapting to technologies such as Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) has redefined the way we conceive and manage network infrastructures. SDN is a network architecture that promotes the use of a singular controller, allowing dynamic, flexible, and programmable network management. Having optimal paths and allocation of resources decided on properly structured devices enhances failure tolerance and adaptation to changing demand. Using its control plane, SDN supports data plane programmability, integrates and manages SmartNICs, supports ZTP for automatic onboarding, and simplifies virtual router deployment and NFV orchestration.

This work presents a new SDN architecture that exceeds the current state-of-the-art by introducing support for the deployment of whiteboxes with network operating systems running in the cloud. Moreover, the whitebox is automatically installed and configured through zero-touch provisioning during bootstrap. Additionally, the whitebox integrates a dynamically configurable SmartNIC capable of executing traffic analysis pipelines on mirrored flows to ensure line-rate security. To achieve this, TeraFlowSDN is enhanced with capabilities for cloud-based NOS provisioning, ZTP-driven configuration, and drivers for managing the whitebox, its SmartNIC, and the flow analysis engine powered by NVIDIA Morpheus. Together, these innovations provide the first open-source implementation that unifies SmartNICs, NOS, and NFV orchestration within ETSI TeraFlowSDN, validated experimentally in the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed.

To better position 6GMICROSDN within the current state-of-the-art, Table 1 provides a comparative analysis against other prominent research efforts in SmartNIC-enabled SDN. While previous works like P4-NetFPGA focused primarily on low-level packet processing via FPGAs, they often lack integration with cloud-native orchestration platforms like ETSI OSM [7]. Similarly, existing SDN frameworks such as ONOS rely on centralized polling or limited DPU management, which struggle with the vendor-agnostic Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) and high-frequency event-driven telemetry required for 6G [8].

Table 1. Comparison of 6GMICROSDN with related SmartNIC and SDN frameworks.

Feature	P4-NetFPGA [7]	ONOS [8]	6GMICROSDN
<i>Mgmt. Protocol</i>	Thrift/CLI	NETCONF	YANG/RESTCONF
<i>Offload Target</i>	FPGA	DPU/white-box NIC	GPU/DPU (Morpheus)
<i>NFV Orch.</i>	None	Limited	Full (ETSI OSM)
<i>Control Plane</i>	Static	Distributed	Unified (TeraFlowSDN)
<i>ZTP Support</i>	No	No	Yes (ONIE/YANG)
<i>Telemetry Mode</i>	Low-freq	Streaming/event-driven	SSE/Event-driven

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2.1 presents the system architecture of the proposed 6GMICROSDN framework, detailing the integration of SmartNIC control, NOS lifecycle automation, and NFV orchestration. Section 2.2 describes the data models and implementation details that enable model-driven interaction across the SDN, SmartNIC, and cloud domains. Section 2.3 introduces the workflows. Moreover, Section 3 shows the results found. Finally, Section 4 provides a critical discussion of operational insights, limitations, future research directions, and conclusions.

2. Materials and Methods

In the following sections, we present the architecture, data models, and workflows. First, the main architecture is described, then each of these components is described in three parts, corresponding to the following key areas: Smart Network Interface Cards for white-boxes, Zero-touch management of the NOS life cycle, and management of microservices in the cloud for automated deployment of NOS instances.

2.1. Overview of Proposed Architecture

The proposed 6GMICROSDN architecture (Figure 1) focuses on a programmable centralized SDN controller, i.e., ETSI TeraFlowSDN, which is able to orchestrate, deploy, and secure network services across cloud and edge infrastructures. TeraFlowSDN interacts with the service orchestrator, i.e., ETSI OSM (Open Source Mano), to automate the lifecycle management of virtualized network functions such as virtual routers and security appliances. In addition, the architecture supports the installation and configuration of NOS on whitebox network hardware using standardized models. The installation and configuration are performed based on Zero-Touch Provisioning that supports automation and configuration without manual intervention. Moreover, at the network edge, the architecture expands the control plane to SmartNICs, where the traffic analysis and anomalous behavior detection are deployed directly on the data plane. By integrating the cloud orchestration, whitebox control, and SmartNICs-based AI acceleration under the TeraFlowSDN controller, the architecture provides a flexible framework that is able to dynamically manage, control, and secure network resources. This high-level architecture is divided into three parts: CLOUD for virtual network function (VNF) orchestration, NOS for whitebox device configuration, and SmartNICs for edge-level security and traffic processing.

Figure 1. High-level 6GMICROSDN architecture.

The main components in the architecture are described below:

1. **TeraFlowSDN:** It is an advanced open-source, cloud-native controller developed by ETSI Software Development Group TeraFlowSDN. TeraFlowSDN is based on a microservices architecture with the main objective of supporting future networks beyond 5G. Thus providing scalability, self-healing, load-balancing, and integrity [9]. Moreover, Figure 2 represents the architecture of TeraFlowSDN. The ETSI TeraFlowSDN architecture is built around several key microservices. First, the Context module maintains all network state and configuration data in a scalable, distributed SQL backend designed for efficient parallel access. Second, the South-Bound Interface (SBI) module communicates with the underlying network devices through a set of interchangeable drivers, enabled by a dedicated Driver API that simplifies the integration of new protocols and data models. Third, the Service module handles the selection, configuration, and activation of connectivity services via the SBI. It supports extensibility through pluggable Service Handlers, each conforming to a defined Service Handler API, allowing quick incorporation of new service types. Fourth, the Path Computation (PathComp) module hosts a variety of routing and path-finding algorithms and exposes an Algorithm API to allow further expansion; the Service module relies on PathComp to compute the routes needed for each connectivity service. Fifth, the North-Bound Interface (NBI) acts as the intermediary between the platform's internal gRPC/protobuf mechanisms and external REST-style interactions, offering REST-API access for systems, primarily those leveraging RESTCONF. Finally, a Web-based User Interface is provided to visualize network information and to submit operational commands to the different TeraFlowSDN components. Besides those core components, additional components for particular flavors of the TeraFlowSDN controller, such as CyberSecurity, Automation, Optical Network Control, or Quantum Key Distribution, might be deployed [10].

Figure 2. TeraFlowSDN architecture [11].

2. OpenStack: It is an open source platform for managing a huge number of resources, such as networking, computing, and storage. It is a popular platform in both public and private clouds for the deployment of infrastructure-as-a-service. The control can be exposed via a graphical user interface, command-line tools, or using REST APIs [12].
3. NVIDIA Morpheus: It is an open-source development and programming environment based on the use of AI to enable the development of new cybersecurity functionalities, allowing the inspection of IP traffic in data center environments. The development environment Morpheus allows groups of developers to build their own pipelines based on pre-trained AI models and features, with the aim of covering different use cases in the cybersecurity area. Morpheus pipeline execution can be reused to offer a wide range of functionalities such as dynamic protection, real-time telemetry, and more [13].

2.1.1. Smart Network Interface Cards for Whiteboxes

TeraFlowSDN's capabilities are extended to manage, configure, and monitor SmartNICs as programmable edge data plane elements. This architecture is based on standardized RESTCONF/NETCONF interfaces, allowing for model-driven control and interoperability with other domains managed by SDN. Figure 3's architecture is composed of three layers, which are TeraFlowSDN, the Morpheus Agent (local management agent), and the SmartNIC: NVIDIA BlueField-2 MT42822 SmartNIC (NVIDIA, Santa Clara, CA, USA) (hardware DPU/GPU). TeraFlowSDN controller functions as the "brain" of the entire system and controls SmartNICs' resources through the SBI. A specific SmartNIC driver exists within TeraFlowSDN that creates the logic required for the RESTCONF client. This allows the controller to send commands to the SmartNIC in order to configure, start, or stop pipelines and subscribe to event notifications at runtime. The Morpheus Agent resides on the host machine connected to the SmartNIC. The agent converts TeraFlowSDN's requests into executable code for the SmartNIC hardware, while ensuring compliance with the schema and providing local state management. SmartNIC Hardware (DPU/GPU) executes packet processing pipelines, performs traffic analysis, and detects anomalies using the NVIDIA Morpheus framework. SmartNIC hardware reduces latency and CPU usage associated with deep packet inspection, encryption, and inference by accelerating these processes in the data plane.

This architecture enables closed-loop control, enabling the controller to configure the SmartNICs and receive continuous telemetry and alerting information to make real-time orchestration decisions. The architecture aligns completely with the intent-driven multi-domain orchestration vision of 6GMICROSDN, enabling SmartNICs to be used as programmable, AI-enabled edge devices in 6G-ready networks.

Figure 3. SmartNICs architecture.

2.1.2. Zero-Touch Management of the NOS Life Cycle

The architecture in Figure 4 is intended to support a ZTP service for whitebox switches by automatically provisioning and managing these switches throughout their lifecycle. The components of this architecture are: whitebox, which refers to the physical switching hardware that may arrive at the customer site with no operating system installed or an operating system that has a very small “installer” in place, such as ONIE; the ZTP Agent, which will act as a mediation and translation layer between the whitebox and the provisioning backend. It provides a vendor-neutral interface to the ZTP Server on the NBI and provides the necessary NOS-specific interfaces to the whitebox on the southbound interface, for example, HTTP endpoints or command-line interfaces; the ZTP Server (On TeraFlowSDN), which will store NOS images and configuration templates, manage the provisioning status of the whiteboxes, and may also be tied into a higher-level SDN controller; the DHCP Server, which will provide the management IP addresses assigned to the whitebox and send the ZTP Agent URL via DHCP options. These components allow the architecture to be vendor-independent, yet support multiple NOS platforms, for example, SONiC, ONL, Cumulus Linux, or OcNOS. This approach was implemented and validated using the SONiC NOS as a reference platform; however, the overall architecture is not dependent upon SONiC and can be adapted to other NOS platforms with minor modifications.

Figure 4. NOS architecture.

2.1.3. Management of Microservices in the Cloud for Automated Deployment of NOS Instances

Figure 5 represents the cloud architecture that focuses on an orchestration methodology based on the microservices architecture of TeraFlowSDN’s cloud-native framework. This was combined with an NFV orchestration stack that consisted of OpenStack as the Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) and OSM as the NFV orchestrator. TeraFlowSDN was implemented as a cloud-native SDN controller with several microservices, including the context database, SBI, NBI, service orchestration, and a new extended microservice referred to as `OSMClient` to interact with OSM. The `OSM_NBI` microservice provides REST-based interfaces inside TeraFlowSDN that would allow the controller to request an instance of a Network Service Instance (NSI), check the status of a NSI, or remove a NSI as required. The `OSM_NBI` microservice internally communicates with the `OSM_Client` microservice; the `OSM_Client` then uses the `OSM_SOL005_NBI` to perform all lifecycle-related functions on the cloud infrastructure for the VNFs.

Figure 5. Cloud architecture.

2.2. Data Models

This section introduces the data models that underpin the model-driven management and orchestration capabilities of the 6GMICROSDN framework across the SmartNIC, NOS, and cloud domains. First, the **SmartNIC data model** defines the configuration, state, and event structures that enable the controller to manage SmartNIC pipelines through

standardized YANG-based interfaces. Second, the **zero-touch provisioning data model** describes how whitebox devices exchange installation and configuration information with the ZTP server in a vendor-agnostic manner using YANG schemas. Finally, the **cloud service data models**—including the VNF Descriptor (VNFD), Network Service Descriptor (NSD), and Network Slice Template (NST)—define how network and cloud resources are described, instantiated, and managed within the NFV orchestration domain. Together, these models ensure structural consistency, interoperability, and full lifecycle automation across physical, virtual, and cloud-native resources.

2.2.1. Data Models for Smart Network Interface Cards for Whiteboxes

The data model for the SmartNICs management was formally specified by the *naudit-morpheus* YANG module, where the parameters for all configurations, states, and events were defined [14]. It defines an overall structure that can be used for both RESTCONF and NETCONF communication to ensure the ability to interact with the SmartNIC management system, as well as other SDN system components. These three key components are used in creating a design for this model: (1) modular abstraction, enabling each stage of the pipeline to have its own independent definition; (2) intention-based configuration, where the controller defines ‘what’ is to be achieved as opposed to ‘how’ it should be performed; (3) hardware decoupling, where the high level control will remain independent of how a particular GPU or DPU addresses memory [15].

- */config container*: The configuration container contains the configuration for SmartNIC pipeline’s run-time behavior, i.e., which traffic types will be processed; how many models will be processed together in a batch; what is the size of the traffic stream (i.e., how long); and how the SmartNIC will act during the run-time of the pipeline. At this time, the config container uses simple parameters to define the pipeline; however, it is designed to be extended to accommodate more complex multi-stage AI pipelines. By creating a pipeline descriptor that models the pipeline as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) of connected pipeline stages, the framework will be able to support advanced security workflows, such as model ensembles or versioned AI stages, without losing compatibility with the existing RESTCONF clients [16].
- */state container*: This container includes read-only data that represents the operational status of the SmartNIC, e.g., how many pipelines are running, and what is the utilization of each resource on the SmartNIC [17].
- */start and /stop actions*: These actions enable the controller to issue commands to start/stop the pipeline execution remotely, so that TeraFlowSDN can turn on/off workloads on the SmartNIC at any time. The Morpheus agent acts as a local reconciliation engine to translate the stateless YANG declarations into stateful hardware executions. When the agent receives a configuration, it runs a state machine (prepared, running, and draining) to map the high-level intent into the low-level hardware operations (e.g., prepare memory buffers, load model weights onto GPU, bind GPUNetIO queues/rings at DOCA).
- */detection-event and /pipeline-error notifications*: These are implemented using Server-Sent Events (SSE), and they provide the controller with an event-based mechanism to receive updates about when a security anomaly/detection has been detected by SmartNIC, or when a run-time error occurs.

Each of these operations uses the RESTCONF/NETCONF protocols and the standard YANG data encoding for its payload. The configuration requests will be sent as JSON or XML payloads to the RESTCONF interface of the SmartNIC, whereas the notifications will be received asynchronously by TFS using SSE. In general, this model-driven approach for SmartNIC management will provide high levels of validation, interoperability, and

automation for managing the lifecycle of the SmartNIC. The data model files can be found at [18].

2.2.2. Data Models for Zero-Touch Management of the NOS Life Cycle

ZTP supports the provision of vendor-agnostic NOS in a zero-touch manner across different NOS platforms, utilizing an exchange of provisioning data between the ZTP agent and server via YANG-based data models to define how the provisioning data will be exchanged between the two components. A YANG-based data model abstracts the installation, configuration, and lifecycle attributes of a device into structurally independent attributes from a specific NOS implementation. Core attributes within this data model include: (i) `ztp_server_url`, which identifies the URL of the provisioning backend service; (ii) `nos_image_url`, which identifies the NOS firmware or OS image to be installed by the ZTP agent upon bootstrapping; (iii) `config_script_url`, which references the provisioning script or configuration template to be executed by the ZTP agent after installation; (iv) `allowed_ip_range`, which defines the authorized management or site network(s) for validation purposes; and (v) `device_state`, which captures the current state of the device's lifecycle (discovered, installing, configuring, operational). These structural representations enable the ZTP Server to select dynamic configurations for each device based on metadata, while the ZTP Agent interprets generic instructions provided by the ZTP Server into the actual NOS-specific provisioning action to complete the zero-touch provisioning process. As such, the use of these data structures allows the same ZTP Server to operate with multiple NOS families (SONiC, ONL, Cumulus Linux, and OcnOS) while requiring minimal changes to accommodate the various NOS implementations. The data model files can be found at [19].

2.2.3. Data Models for Management of Microservices in the Cloud for Automated Deployment of NOS Instances

Service descriptions such as VNFD, NSD, and NST provide the basis for cloud domain, network service, and slice deployments through standardization based upon ETSI NFV descriptors. The VNFD describes the resources required for a VNF, its internal and external connections, references to images that include the software running on it, and lifecycle operations to be used during deployment of a virtualized network function. The NSD defines how two or more VNFs can be connected together to create a full network service, which includes definitions for virtual links between VNFs and deployment flavors. The NST represents the logical groupings of both network and cloud resources needed to provision an NSI, and is composed of the slice's service type, QoS parameters, and each of the NSDs that define it. Through these service description models, OSM can uniformly translate service requests into infrastructure and allocate cloud resources using OpenStack, while at the same time providing TeraFlowSDN with the information necessary to coordinate the network-level orchestration. Overall, they represent the foundation for the system's ability to manage the provisioning of physical networks (via ZTP) and virtual services (via NSI/NSSI). The data model files can be found at [20].

2.3. Workflows for Edge Microservices with SDN Whiteboxes

This section details the operational workflows that enable end-to-end automation across the three main technological domains of the proposed 6GMICROSDN framework. First, the **SmartNIC integration workflow** describes the complete lifecycle management of programmable network interface cards, from device onboarding to real-time monitoring and decommissioning. Second, the **zero-touch management workflow for the NOS lifecycle** explains the automated installation and configuration process of whitebox network operating systems (e.g., SONiC) using a standardized ZTP mechanism. Finally,

the **cloud orchestration workflow** illustrates how TeraFlowSDN coordinates with OSM and OpenStack to deploy and manage virtualized network functions (VNFs), network services, and network slices. Together, these workflows demonstrate how the proposed architecture achieves full-stack automation across data plane, control plane, and cloud infrastructure layers.

2.3.1. Workflow for Smart Network Interface Cards for Whiteboxes

SmartNIC integration workflow describes the complete lifecycle of SmartNIC device onboarding and operational phases, which includes the end-of-life de-configuration. Figure 6 shows the workflow related to SmartNICs, which is defined in several steps: TeraFlowSDN first initiates the AddDevice operation to register the SmartNIC host. TeraFlowSDN will then identify the Morpheus Agent's RESTCONF endpoint and connect it with the SmartNIC driver once the host is registered. Next, TeraFlowSDN generates the ConfigureDevice function that targets the URL/restconf/data/naudit-morpheus:morpheus/config. The RESTCONF POST request will contain the SmartNIC pipeline parameters. After that, once the configuration request is received, the Morpheus Agent validates the configuration received against the YANG schema of the agent, updates the agent's local database, and initiates the execution of the SmartNIC pipeline on the DPU/GPU. The SmartNIC pipeline processes traffic classification, anomaly detection, and generates telemetry data at line rate. Moreover, during the runtime phase, the agent continuously sends real-time notifications (detection-event, pipeline-error) to TeraFlowSDN through SSE. These notifications will populate TeraFlowSDN's monitoring and policy components. This allows TeraFlowSDN to perform automated adjustments and/or re-configuration of the SmartNIC when necessary. Finally, when any changes to service parameters occur and/or devices are deactivated, TeraFlowSDN will send RESTCONF PATCH or DELETE requests to update or delete the configuration of the SmartNIC. The agent will clean up after the reconfiguration/deletion, update its state database, and stop the pipeline associated with SmartNIC.

Figure 6. SmartNICs workflow.

2.3.2. Workflow for Zero-Touch Management of the NOS Life Cycle

Figure 7 shows the NOS lifecycle workflow. The workflow is described as follows: First, the whitebox boots its ONIE environment and sends a DHCP Discover. The DHCP server replies with an IP, gateway, and the ZTP Agent URL (via options such as 114/67). Then ONIE requests the ZTP Agent over HTTP/TFTP to have the appropriate NOS image that includes metadata (model, vendor, serial, CPU arch). The ZTP Agent asks the ZTP Server via gRPC; the server selects the correct image and returns its descriptor/URL, and then the agent sends the image back to ONIE. ONIE writes the image to local storage, verifies it, and reboots into the newly installed NOS. After reboot, the NOS starts its ZTP client and sends another DHCP Discover to obtain the location of its configuration script (normally via option 67 pointing to the ZTP Agent). The NOS looks for the provisioning file (e.g., ztp.json) from the ZTP Agent; the agent retrieves the right file from the ZTP Server over gRPC and returns it to the NOS via HTTP/TFTP. Finally, the NOS applies the configuration (e.g., config_db.json changes), brings services and interfaces up, and completes zero-touch end-to-end provisioning.

Figure 7. NOS workflow.

2.3.3. Workflow for Management of Microservices in the Cloud for Automated Deployment of NOS Instances

Cloud workflow uses an integrated orchestration process that combines OpenStack as a VIM for infrastructure, OSM as the NFV orchestrator for orchestration, and TeraFlowSDN as the SDN controller for the SDN control layer. OpenStack is provisioned and configured using management networks, flavors, key pairs, and images to enable the deployment of VNF. Then, OSM configures OpenStack as a VIM account and allocates both compute and network resources. The workflow related to the cloud Figure 8 is described: TeraFlowSDN,

through the OSM_NBI component and OSM_Client component, requests a network service instantiation from OSM, then OSM allocates the network resources on OpenStack. Moreover, OpenStack confirms the resource allocation to OSM, which confirms to TeraFlowSDN that the NSI is running. Next, NST is created and linked to the network service on OSM. Then, TeraFlowSDN requests the network slice instantiation from OSM which allocates the resources on OpenStack according to NST specification. Finally, OpenStack notifies OSM that the resources are ready, and OSM confirms to TeraFlowSDN that the slice is active. As a conclusion, the cloud workflow provides end-to-end orchestration of cloud/network layers by allowing full automation of the deployment of VNFs, network services, and slice instances using TeraFlowSDN, in conjunction with OSM and OpenStack.

Figure 8. Cloud workflow.

3. Results

This section is divided into three parts. It provides a description of the experimental results, their interpretation, and the experimental conclusions that can be drawn. The experimental validation took place at CTTC's ADRENALINE testbed, an SDN-enabled disaggregated packet-optical network comprising access, metro, and core segments, and extended with edge, regional, and central-office data centers.

3.1. Lifecycle Convergence

The experimental results obtained at the CTTC testbed have demonstrated the effectiveness of the work proposed. Integrating a ZTP into an SDN controller environment helped in achieving the installation of the network operating system and configuring it in a whitebox. As analyzed in the ZTP Timing results Figure 9, the system autonomously detected the NOS-less whitebox and completed the image retrieval and installation process. This framework showed that through the configuration settings, we can provision Layer 2 and Layer 3 Virtual Private Network services supporting intent-driven provisioning. These results showed that using standardized data models with automation through SDN can improve the performance of the network, especially supporting next-generation programmable 6G transport networks.

Figure 9. Breakdown of the zero-touch provisioning process for the SONiC-based whitebox emulator.

3.2. Operational Agility

The combination of TeraFlowSDN, OSM, and OpenStack was also tested at the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed. The test was performed on a certain example, which included a SONiC virtual router. It was shown that the above-mentioned architecture in Figure 5 enabled the complete automation of the deployment of both virtualized network services and network slices. Figure 10 illustrates the communication from the NBI of TeraFlowSDN using the OSM client with OSM to do Create, Read, Update, Delete (CRUD) operations concerning network services. Moreover, Figure 11 shows a successful network slice created. Finally, Figure 12 shows that the delete operations were performed within an average of 0.45 s, get operations within 0.77 s, and create within 0.79 s. The operations were repeated 50 times to collect relevant statistical samples. As a conclusion, the test data confirmed that the proposed cloud orchestration architecture will provide reliable and automated provisioning of both VNFs and network slices, and will provide a scalable basis for dynamically deploying services in 6G cloud-native networks.

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Info
REF	10.1.7.197	10.2.29.147	HTTP/JSON	POST /osm-api/NS_Services HTTP/1.1 , JSON (application/json)
0.000655661	10.2.29.147	10.2.29.150	HTTP/JSON	POST /osm-api/NS_Services HTTP/1.1 , JSON (application/json)
75.432967627	10.1.7.197	10.2.29.147	HTTP	GET /osm-api/NS_Services HTTP/1.1
75.433804941	10.2.29.147	10.2.29.150	HTTP	GET /osm-api/NS_Services HTTP/1.1
94.615077118	10.1.7.197	10.2.29.147	HTTP	GET /osm-api/NS_Service/2a8ca49f-f826-4ad9-96cf-5037bd2b3089 HTTP/1.1
94.616392297	10.2.29.147	10.2.29.150	HTTP	GET /osm-api/NS_Service/2a8ca49f-f826-4ad9-96cf-5037bd2b3089 HTTP/1.1
119.821326001	10.1.7.197	10.2.29.147	HTTP	DELETE /osm-api/NS_Service/2a8ca49f-f826-4ad9-96cf-5037bd2b3089 HTTP/1.1
119.822805669	10.2.29.147	10.2.29.150	HTTP	DELETE /osm-api/NS_Service/2a8ca49f-f826-4ad9-96cf-5037bd2b3089 HTTP/1.1

Figure 10. OSM/NBI CRUD request.

Figure 11. Successful network slice on OSM.

Figure 12. Average latency for CRUD operations with error bars representing the standard deviation.

3.3. Edge Analytics Effectiveness

SmartNIC's experimental setup was performed at the CTTC premises on the ADRENALINE testbed. An NVIDIA/Mellanox BlueField-2 MT42822 SmartNIC, an NVIDIA A30 GPU, NVIDIA Morpheus, and TeraFlowSDN were integrated on the same whitebox, whereas a traffic generator was deployed on another host. We integrated NVIDIA's Sensitive Information Detection (SID) pipeline into the BlueField-2 SmartNIC. It was combined with GPUNetIO to direct transfer the packets to the NVIDIA A30 GPU without using the CPU, ensuring low latency. On the other hand, the Morpheus framework runs an SID pipeline to identify sensitive elements such as emails, passwords, or credit card numbers. TeraFlowSDN was deployed to manage the pipeline traffic through RESTCONF-API, enabling control to Morpheus. Latency of intent-based configuration changes was used to evaluate the functionality of the management plane (see Figure 13). The time it took to complete RESTCONF operations (such as retrieving state and dynamically changing the parameters of an AI model) was measured. Simple retrievals averaged 43 ms while complex operations (e.g., set model) needed 95 ms to complete since they involved the initialization of the pipeline after each update. Additionally, the results show how much better this offloading architecture works than a typical host-centric SID pipeline (see Figure 14). For example, CPU usage was at 85% for the SID pipeline, which created a huge bottleneck for other edge services. On the other hand, by offloading the SID pipeline to the SmartNIC and GPU, the host CPU usage was decreased to only 8% or a total of 90.5% less. Therefore, this demonstrates the efficiency of the 6GMICROSDN architecture. A closed-loop control system was also tested; when the traffic generator produced sensitive information, the AI-based SmartNIC detected the elements, autonomously notified TeraFlowSDN via SSE of the state change, and completed the intent-driven management process.

Figure 13. Management latency for dynamic Morpheus pipeline configuration.

Figure 14. Comparison of host CPU load during Sensitive Information Detection (SID).

3.4. Scalability Analysis

The robustness of the 6GMICROSDN framework for high-density 6G network deployment has been evaluated through an analytical scalability analysis based on the use of controller resources. In this study, as demonstrated in Figure 15, the overall performance of the system was analyzed at various node counts ranging from 1 to 50 nodes, and the overhead associated with the management plane was used as empirical data. The results of the study indicated that the Task Processing load (gray) increased linearly with the increase in the number of nodes; however, the Management Overhead (blue) remained sub-linear and only increased from 5 units to 15 units. This type of efficiency is made possible due to the utilization of Server-Sent Events (SSEs), which eliminates the $O(n)$ communication complexity typically found in traditional polling-based SDN systems. Through

the maintenance of constant management overhead, the 6GMICROSDN architecture will prevent controller saturation and ensure stability of operation for very large-scale 6G edge environments and will meet the requirements for distributed control planes of modern orchestration systems [21,22].

Figure 15. Scalability of the 6GMICROSDN framework.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

This paper introduced 6GMICROSDN, a unified architecture for edge microservice deployment and management that seamlessly integrates SmartNICs, whitebox NOS, and cloud-native NFV orchestration within a single software-defined control plane. The proposed framework extends ETSI TeraFlowSDN with (i) a YANG/RESTCONF-based SmartNIC control module for programmable pipeline management and event-driven telemetry, (ii) a vendor-agnostic zero-touch provisioning workflow for NOS lifecycle automation, and (iii) an embedded client for ETSI OSM enabling dynamic offloading of VNFs across the edge–cloud continuum.

Experimental validation in the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed demonstrated the operational efficiency and responsiveness of the proposed system. The SmartNIC-driven event loop enabled real-time anomaly detection and reporting with sub-100 ms responsiveness, while orchestrated service instantiation via OSM achieved end-to-end CRUD operations below one second, even under concurrent configuration updates. It should be noted that the sub-100 ms responsiveness as reported relates to the latency of the Management Plane—the time it takes for an edge-detection of a security event to reach the TeraFlowSDN controller via SSE and be resolved into a Management Decision; whereas Data Plane Latency will remain in the order of microseconds, since the GPU/DPU processes packets at line rate without any CPU involvement. The current RESTCONF/HTTP-based Control Loop provides a robust, standard means of orchestrating intent, but due to its Request/Response nature, it may introduce limitations in future 6G use cases where deterministic, high-frequency interactions are required (e.g., sub-ms control loops) [23]. Future work to further enhance the performance of the system relative to what has been achieved through this research can be explored by developing the integration with advanced data-plane programming

technologies, such as in-band telemetry using P4 or instructions carried on SRv6 Headers [24]. These technologies enable the embedding of control signals directly within the headers of data-plane packets. Compared to manual configuration workflows, the proposed automation reduced service deployment latency by approximately 80% and improved operational consistency across heterogeneous domains.

By combining in situ packet-level analytics at the SmartNIC with centralized SDN orchestration, 6GMICROSDN achieves measurable reductions in control overhead and enables proactive adaptation to network dynamics. These results confirm the feasibility of intent-based, closed-loop orchestration for 6G-ready edge and transport infrastructures, advancing toward autonomous, self-optimizing network operations.

Future work will extend the current framework toward multi-domain scalability, energy-aware orchestration policies, and integration with AI-driven intent processing and digital twin-assisted assurance models, enabling predictive and sustainable automation for next-generation networks.

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Data Availability Statement: Regarding the technical implementation links in ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) repository: SmartNIC Drivers: <https://labs.etsi.org/rep/tfs/controller/-/tree/master/src/device/service/drivers/smartnic> (accessed on 29 December 2025). This link provides the open source code for the drivers that allow the controller to manage SmartNIC hardware pipelines. ZTP Server Protocol: https://labs.etsi.org/rep/tfs/controller/-/blob/master/proto/ztp_server.proto (accessed on 29 December 2025). This link provides the protocol definition (gRPC/ProtoBuf) for the Zero-Touch Provisioning server used to automate the network operating system (NOS) installation. OSM Client Protocol: https://labs.etsi.org/rep/tfs/controller/-/blob/master/proto/osm_client.proto (accessed on 29 December 2025). This link provides the protocol definition for the interaction between the SDN controller and ETSI OSM for cloud resource orchestration.

Conflicts of Interest: Mohamad Rahhal, Lluís Gifre, Raul Muñoz, and Ricard Vilalta were employed by Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC-CERCA). Pablo Armingol and Oscar González de Dios were employed by Telefonica. Javier Mateos Najari and Rafael Leira Osuna were employed by Naudit. Aitor Zabala was employed by Telcaria. Manuel Angel Jimenez was employed by Eviden. The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

6G	Sixth Generation
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DPU	Data Processing Unit
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit

HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
MANO	Management and Orchestration
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NIC	Network Interface Card
NOS	Network Operating System
ONIE	Open Network Install Environment
OSM	Open Source MANO
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SmartNIC	Smart Network Interface Card
SSE	Server-Sent Events
VNF	Virtual Network Function
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

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